

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D.5.2 Data Management Plan for E-RIHS ERIC

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ABSTRACT

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the established data management practices and protocols that E-RIHS and its partners shall adhere to in order to organize, preserve, and share the data generated within the infrastructure. The primary objective is to ensure that all data and processes managed by E-RIHS are as open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) as possible, while maintaining necessary confidentiality and protection. This document will be periodically updated to reflect any new insights, changes, or enhancements in data management strategies as E-RIHS evolves and is to be considered as a living document.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Expansion
API	Application Programming Interface - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/API
ARCHLAB	Relates to the notion of “Archive Laboratories” - http://www.iperionhs.eu/archlab/
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire - European Council for Nuclear Research - https://home.cern
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - https://www.cnr.it
DIGILAB	Relates to the notion of “Digital Laboratories” or Digital Tools and services. Can also be used to relate to more general digital infrastructure issues.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier (https://www.doi.org)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Open_Science_Cloud
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en)
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science - http://www.e-rihs.eu
E-RIHS Central Hub	“It operates as the main access point to the research infrastructure. It provides operational and administrative support to the Director and helps E-RIHS ERIC in the coordination and management activities.” - https://www.e-rihs.eu/organization-and-governance/
E-RIHS IP	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Implementation Phase - E-RIHS IP has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe call HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02, Grant Agreement n. 101079148 .
E-RIHS Knowledge-base	The E-RIHS Knowledge-base is a linked datastore holding all of the metadata describing data and activities related to E-RIHS. At this stage it can be found at: https://data.e-rihs.io/
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable - https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles
FIXLAB	Relates to the notion of “Fixed or large-scale Laboratories”
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation - http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/2016-05-04
HS	Heritage Science
IPERION HS	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science - http://www.iperionhs.eu - IPERION-HS has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 call H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1, under GA 871034
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KIK-IRPA	Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium - Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage - http://www.kikirpa.be
MOLAB	Relates to the notion of “Mobile Laboratories”

	http://www.iperionhs.eu/molab
National Nodes	“The National Nodes (Hubs) ... represent Members and coordinate facilities at the national level. They are managed by their National Coordinators.” - https://www.e-rihs.eu/national-nodes/
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting - https://openarchives.org/pmh/
PID	Persistent Identifier - https://tanc-ahrc.github.io/PIDResources/
REST	REpresentational State Transfer https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

INTRODUCTION

The E-RIHS¹ “European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science” ERIC “European Research Infrastructure Consortium” integrates a range of national facilities, recognized for their expertise in the study of Heritage Science, to create a permanent open infrastructure of institutions and specialist researchers, engaged in collaborative research and providing services to the wider field of Heritage Science.

E-RIHS abides by the DARIAH Heritage Data Re-Use Charter² and will ensure access to data and related services as a core part of current and future research within the infrastructure, specifically to support the ongoing development and expansions of its consortium and future international collaborations.

This E-RIHS Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a general outline of the data collected, generated and used for and by the range of researchers working within E-RIHS along with details of some of the key E-RIHS digital services and guidelines describing how data will be preserved and published. It is organised in relation to the FAIR Data Principles³, was originally guided by the principles of Open Access⁴, has been written in line with the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes and Data Management Policy and will respect the General Data Protection Regulation⁵ (GDPR) provisions. E-RIHS follows the recognised requirements for open science and open publications⁶ and ⁷, collaborates with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁸ in the framework of the SSHOC cluster, will support the development of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)⁹ and contributes to FAIR heritage data.

Unless limited by existing legal restrictions or justified by legitimate interests, all publications and data produced as part of E-RIHS shall be published/released under an open Creative Commons licence, or an agreed equivalent licence.

As noted, before, this DMP is intended as a general guide to data management within E-RIHS. It will evolve, as and when required, as E-RIHS develops, particularly whenever significant changes arise within the management of the consortium and the generation of datasets. For example, new versions of the DMP may be required to provide additional details in relation to the data

¹ <http://www.e-rihs.eu/>

² Heritage Data Reuse Charter: <https://www.dariah.eu/tools-services/data-re-use/>

³ Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_access

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

⁶ Benassi, Laura. (2021, January 16). IPERION HS How to do - Open Science: EU rules and tips (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4444799> - <http://www.iperionhs.eu/publications-2/open-access/>

⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

⁸ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1>

⁹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en

management of any changes in the ERIC or the additions of any new types of services to ARCHLAB¹⁰, DIGILAB¹¹, FIXLAB¹² and MOLAB¹³. It is envisaged that this DMP will be linked to more detailed or specific DMPs created for individual E-RIHS National Nodes¹⁴, services providers and future related research and access projects.

GENERAL E-RIHS DATA

The main class of data, being considered under E-RIHS, will be raw and interpreted data created and or processed, relating to the technical or analytical examination of heritage works, by the access providers and researchers working within E-RIHS and by any other research activities carried out under the framework of E-RIHS. However, the notion of “E-RIHS data” also covers a wider range of digital assets, including publications, reports, survey data, documentation, software and more. A plan for a detailed list of E-RIHS data and data types will be discussed with the National Nodes to determine the best way to construct and maintain it in the framework of E-RIHS as the ERIC is formed and develops. All the data created, either new or as a derivative of existing data, by E-RIHS members, researchers, staff, and supported projects and activities, will be considered as Results (Foreground Data) and must be published and made accessible following the best practice guidelines provided by projects developed by the E-RIHS community¹⁵. However, the meaning and context of this new data will often rely on supporting Background Data. Some of this Background Data, such as the metadata describing and identifying the heritage works that have been examined, should be considered as Required Background Data and will also need to be published, or made FAIR, to ensure that any generated Results (Foreground Data) can be fully usable and exploited.

¹⁰ “ARCHLAB provides access to organized scientific information in largely unpublished datasets from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions.” For more information and past examples see: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/archlab/>

¹¹ DIGILAB will be catalogue of technical services supported by an advanced digital infrastructure within E-RIHS, providing remote access to extensive digitized heritage data and analytical tools. It will aim to connect key digital repositories and laboratories across Europe under a unified management structure. DIGILAB will support heritage scientists by offering access to services, VREs and tools to allow researchers to exploit high-resolution images, 3D models, spectroscopic data, and other digital resources. Its services are expected to include advanced data processing, virtual laboratories, and interoperable platforms, enhancing the analysis, preservation, and interpretation of cultural heritage through seamless collaboration and data sharing.

¹² “The goal of FIXLAB is to provide access for the Heritage Science (HS) community to key fixed research facilities and to the associated scientific experience of their staff that develop and maintain sophisticated state-of-the-art instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry.” For more information and past examples see: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/fixlab/>

¹³ “MOLAB (MOBILE LABORATORY) is a world-class distributed infrastructure which consists of key laboratories across 10 European countries providing coherent access, under a unified management structure, to a set of mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites.” For more information and past examples see: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/molab/>

¹⁴ <https://www.e-rihs.eu/national-nodes/>

¹⁵ For more information relating to the actual process of making data open see: Benassi, Laura. (2021, January 16). IPERION HS How to do - Open Science: EU rules and tips (Version 1.0). Zenodo, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459152>

This document is intended to address the aspects related to research “access to” and “use of” E-RIHS Data. Article 9 of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes regulates Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), while issues related to data ownership and usage are addressed in the E-RIHS ERIC Data Management Policy and may require further consideration if necessary.

Results (Foreground Data)

‘Results’ means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.¹⁶

Within E-RIHS the term “Results (Foreground Data)” can be understood to include all stages of data creation and processing, along with all the metadata required to identify, validate, and potentially re-use the data.

Within E-RIHS Results (Foreground Data) can be divided into three main sections:

1. **Published data:** this will include published articles, relating to E-RIHS results, along with all raw and processed data needed to validate the published work. Sufficient documentation and metadata will also be included to ensure that the work can be identified, accessed, and re-used. All E-RIHS published data will be released under open access, complete with an appropriate re-use licence and all the required supporting metadata, at the time of publication or after an agreed embargo of **6 months (12 months for publications in the social sciences and humanities)** if required as part of the open access publications process.
2. **Reports and Documentation:** this will include all non-formally published reports and documentation relating to the work carried out as part of E-RIHS activities. Where practicable and appropriate these will be published on the E-RIHS website, within the E-RIHS Knowledge-base and within an appropriate [data repository](#). This will include all the completed “**User Reports**”¹⁷ generated as a result of E-RIHS accesses. Where appropriate, these data will be published within **6 months** of the completion of the related work.
3. **Any other data:** created or produced during work as part of E-RIHS, including all the “tangible or intangible” assets not included as Published data. The publication of non “published data” is not required by the EU, but it is strongly encouraged by the EU. For valuable E-RIHS work that generates exploitable data, it is recommended that this data be published and made accessible within 24 months of its production or within 12 months of the completion of the specific related project or activity, whichever comes first.

Please note that as described below, within the section on [Making data FAIR in the E-RIHS ERIC](#), where the publication of Results (Foreground Data) is limited or restricted by existing IPR or by defined and documented “legitimate interest”, it is still very important to register that the data have been created and do still exist. In this case the metadata defining and describing the Results (Foreground Data), along with details describing the scope and accessibility of said data, needs to

¹⁶ Annotated model GA (version 1.0, 1 May 2024), see Article 16.2, page 180:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

¹⁷ An updated description will be provided on the E-RIHS website based on the information already provided by projects developed by the E-RIHS community, see <http://www.iperionhs.eu/after-access/> and https://www.iperionhs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/IPERION-HS_User-Report_TEMPLATE.pdf

be published as an empty data set. If circumstances change in the future, then the data can be added as a new version of the existing empty data set.

It is the responsibility of E-RIHS and its members to ensure that all E-RIHS results (Foreground Data) are preserved and made accessible, where applicable, for at least 5 years after their creation, and continue to be maintained for as long as they remain relevant to ensure they adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles.

To ensure the continued accessibility of E-RIHS data, the responsibility falls on the data owners unless this task is delegated to the E-RIHS Central Hub or a similar body. This responsibility includes updating records of published data and, in more extreme cases, migrating data between repositories.

To support this process, a comprehensive list of E-RIHS data stewardship recommendations and guidelines will be developed and made available in the future. This will provide clear instructions and best practices to assist data owners in maintaining data accessibility and integrity.

Background Data¹⁸

‘Background’ means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results.¹⁹

Within E-RIHS this simple definition is also extended to include all external related data potentially needed in relation to E-RIHS activities, so it will include resources created during the period of the relevant E-RIHS activities but outside of and not directly supported by the E-RIHS activities. Therefore, in the context of E-RIHS this can represent a wide range of tangible and intangible assets held by researchers, access providers and E-RIHS users. The key issues prior to the commencement of any defined research or access activity is to **identify** what Background Data are **required for the work** and ensure that appropriate **access rights** are available.

Background Data are covered by existing IPR and licence restrictions, as defined in Article 9 of the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes and may not always be in a format that facilitates efficient re-use. As part of the preparation for any defined piece of E-RIHS research or access provision, specifically ARCHLAB accesses, it is important to clearly identify what Background Data may be required and what access rights or licence limitations may be in place and to ensure that any Required Background Data will be available and licenced for future use in relation to the Results (Foreground Data) created during any E-RIHS activity.

REQUIRED BACKGROUND DATA

Required Background Data is defined as the minimal amount of information/knowledge required to ensure that any Results (Foreground Data) produced in relation to E-RIHS can be understood, put in context, and re-used. The level of detail required here will vary depending on the nature and scope of the work being carried out, but these data will need to be at least made available under an open

¹⁸ For more information see: <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/news/how-define-and-manage-background-horizon-2020>

¹⁹ Annotated model GA (version 1.0, 1 May 2024), see Article 16.1, page 180:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

licence for academic research. A fuller list of examples will be constructed and maintained by E-RIHS as the ERIC is formed and develops, but initially the best examples relate to the:

- Key metadata required to identify and find any objects/works of art examined or studied within E-RIHS activities or related to samples examined or studied within E-RIHS activities. These metadata can be descriptive, facilitating resource discovery but could, depending on the specific dataset, also relate to technical metadata of related materials, equipment, or measurements.
- An image, of sufficient size²⁰, to clearly illustrate any objects/works of art/sample examined or studied within E-RIHS activities, if one is not created during the E-RIHS activities.
- Inventory, short summary, access detail and/or references for any documentation, reports, publications, databases, or archives referenced or used within the work.
- Inventory, short summary and access detail for any Background datasets referenced or used within the work. It is recommended, where possible, and if they have not been already published, that these datasets are also published in an appropriate, open data repository or similar institutional system to facilitate further research activities, subject to existing licencing and IPR restrictions.

E-RIHS Management Data

As part of the general running of E-RIHS and the ongoing tracking of E-RIHS activities, milestones and any related reports or recommendations, management related data will be produced, collected and archived, by the E-RIHS Central Hub and various E-RIHS partners and boards. E-RIHS management data will include, but will not be limited to, all the supporting documents created during the general running of E-RIHS, for example, official meeting minutes and agendas, reports, public financial documents/summaries, the E-RIHS Statutes, deliverables and other exploitable research outputs, presentations, E-RIHS media files (templates, logos, etc.) and other related documents.

To manage and develop all these documents in a shared location, open to all the relevant E-RIHS ERIC members and boards, E-RIHS has set up a dedicated Teams/SharePoint virtual environment hosted by CNR. This resource is a closed working environment and provides shared file management, storage, and preservation along with a discussion forum. The suitability of this solution will continue to be assessed, as E-RIHS develops and grows, to ensure it continues to meet the needs of the E-RIHS community.

All public versions of completed documents, reports, recommendations, procedures, etc. will also be published via the main E-RIHS data repository and/or on the public E-RIHS website²¹.

All completed private documents, reports, recommendations, procedures, etc. will be managed by the Central Hub and stored within a shared E-RIHS virtual environment. The development of a public

²⁰ The specific dimensions here will be further discussed, if required, as new versions of this DMP are created, but at this time sufficient size is indicated as big enough to be printed in a report at half page width or height at reasonable quality, approximately 150 DPI. This equates to an image resized to fit within the bounding box of 600x800px.

²¹ <https://www.e-rihs.eu/>

registry of all closed data/documents, including key metadata describing the data/documents - responsible person, summary, key words, reason for privacy, IPR holder, etc. will be explored as E-RIHS develops.

The E-RIHS administrative and management data will be maintained going forward in the E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub.

User Data

During its day-to-day activities E-RIHS has the potential to gather a range of personal data, related to access applications, exploitations and disseminations activities, publications, data records and general correspondence. These data will be stored and used in accordance with gathered consent and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) legislation. The storage and use of these data, required beyond any initially agreed periods, will require separate written agreement.

A detailed description of how these data are gathered and managed is planned to be added to the current E-RIHS privacy and cookies policies, available via the E-RIHS public website.

Some user data, specifically related to completed E-RIHS accesses and collaborative research activities, will be published, as part of the access or research agreements, within dedicated access reports, publications, and other dissemination material.

Dissemination, Training, Presentations and Other Data

PRESENTATIONS

All public E-RIHS presentations will be published via the selected E-RIHS Data Repositories(s) and/or presented on the public E-RIHS website²². Where possible this will include links to online presentations or video files of the actual presentation. Defining a consistent approach to categorising or keywording presentation data will continue to be developed during ongoing E-RIHS activities. All private or restricted presentations will be managed along with other closed management data. A list or registry of presentations given in relation to E-RIHS will be managed by the E-RIHS Central Hub.

TRAINING MATERIAL

New training or educational material created as part of the work of E-RIHS will be managed following the procedures for other E-RIHS data and published under open access where possible, limited or restricted by existing IPR or by defined and documented "legitimate interest". The use and management of existing training material will be subject to specific Background data agreements or existing licenses. A list or registry of training resources used within E-RIHS will be managed by the E-RIHS Central Hub. The HS (Heritage Science) Academy is currently responsible for gathering and publishing training related video material.

SOCIAL MEDIA

A range of social media accounts have been established to support and expand the activities of E-RIHS, the data hosted and housed on these platforms is generally managed by the individual respective platforms.

²² <https://www.e-rihs.eu/>

- **Facebook:** <https://www.facebook.com/e.ri.heritage.science> - Used for general dissemination and social engagement. The account is maintained by the E-RIHS Central Hub and the data are managed by the Facebook platform²³.
- **X (formally Twitter):** <https://twitter.com/ErihsEu> - Used for general dissemination activities and connecting with related projects and researchers. The account is maintained by the E-RIHS Central Hub and the data are managed by the X platform²⁴.
- **YouTube:** <https://www.youtube.com/c/ERIHSEU> - E-RIHS YouTube Channel is used to publish and share short videos created in relation to E-RIHS. The account is maintained by the E-RIHS Central Hub and the data are managed by the YouTube platform²⁵.
- **LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/e-rihs/> - This dedicated LinkedIn company has been setup to act as an E-RIHS user forum. The account is maintained by the E-RIHS Central Hub²⁶.

SHORT VIDEOS

In addition to publishing videos on YouTube, any pre-publication, internal demo or restricted videos will be stored on private E-RIHS virtual environment. Any details and documentation relating to these videos will be stored with them and managed alongside all of the other management data. Where possible and appropriate these additional videos will also be published on YouTube or as part of the public website, as E-RIHS develops.

Data Repositories

To simplify the process of the publishing E-RIHS data in an open access repository, E-RIHS has set up a specific community site on the Zenodo²⁷ infrastructure.

- <https://zenodo.org/communities/e-rihs>

All public E-RIHS data can be deposited with Zenodo following the instructions they provide²⁸. To improve discoverability standardised keyword or subject terms will continue to be examined within E-RIHS. Alternative local data repositories, including institutional repositories, can also be used if they are compliant with EU obligations. More details and tools to help with this process will be provided as relevant guideline FAQs that will be published on the E-RIHS website²⁹.

Also, all additional local and institutional data repositories used to host E-RIHS data will be registered with the E-RIHS Central Hub. Examples can include but are not limited to:

²³ <https://www.facebook.com/about/privacy>

²⁴ <https://twitter.com/en/tos>

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/t/terms>

²⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/legal/user-agreement>

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

²⁸ <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/>

²⁹ This document will be an updated version of: Benassi, Laura. (2021, January 16). IPERION HS How to do - Open Science: EU rules and tips (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459152>

Making data Findable

Making data **Findable** relates to ensuring that data are described with appropriate metadata, is uniquely identified with open PIDs and that the PID can be used to discover the data online. E-RIHS will take the following steps to improve the Findability of the data produced E-RIHS related activities.

- All public E-RIHS data shall be published with clear agreed standardised metadata to aid discoverability. This metadata profile will be based on standard data repository requirements, such as those described within the Datacite Metadata Schema³⁴ and the more specific work being carried out to define the metadata requirements for Heritage Science research which is being published on GitHub³⁵ and used within the E-RIHS Metadata Knowledge-Base.
- Where relevant, existing, published metadata standards will be followed and their use in relation to E-RIHS will be documented.
- When E-RIHS data cannot be published, due to agreed and documented “legitimate interests”, details of and metadata for the data will still be published, along with a description of the conditions that restrict its publication.
- All E-RIHS data will be published with publicly resolvable references or URLs, and it is recommended that this will be in the form of a publicly resolvable Persistent Identifier (PID)³⁶, such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
- Details of all published E-RIHS data and related publications will be aggregated by the E-RIHS Central Hub to form the basis of a registry of exploitable assets. This registry will also be made public.
- Details of E-RIHS data will also be automatically aggregated via a specific OpenAire³⁷ community gateway dedicated to heritage science.³⁸

Figure 2: Findable

Making data openly Accessible

Making data **Accessible** relates to ensuring that data, or at least the metadata defining and describing the data, is retrievable online via standard, documented procedures. FAIR data does not “need” to be open, but its existence does need to be documented and a digital description of it, including any access restrictions do need to be accessible. E-RIHS will take the following steps to improve the Accessibility of the data produced in the project.

³⁴ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

³⁵ <https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema>

³⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persistent_identifier

³⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

³⁸ <https://heritage-science.openaire.eu/>

- All E-RIHS data will be published in a publicly accessible and reliable repository³⁹. As noted, E-RIHS has set up a dedicated community area on Zenodo⁴⁰ to act as a default repository for E-RIHS data.
- In addition to any PIDs assigned by selected data repositories all metadata records stored within the E-RIHS Metadata Knowledge-Base or terms referenced in the E-RIHS Vocabulary Server will be allocated an E-RIHS PID based on the Handle system⁴¹ and provided by the E-RIHS Persistent Identifiers system.
- Metadata describing all E-RIHS data, including any Required Background data, shall be published using open standards whenever practicable.
- Where it is not possible for the actual data to be released, due to agreed and documented “legitimate interests”, details of the data and any required metadata shall still be registered in an appropriate repository to enhance accessibility. These registered details should include information describing where the data can be accessed and what the existing restrictions are on access.
- Where data has been lost, destroyed or is inaccessible, the publication of the data details, including any required metadata, shall be maintained to ensure any references to the data will still resolve to a description of the data.
- When the recommended repository, Zenodo, is not used, selected alternatives should also:
 - Be compliant with EU obligations - this can be verified using the tools provided at: <https://re3data.org>.
 - Provide access to data and metadata via standardised protocols - for example Zenodo provides access via and [REST APIs](#).⁴²
 - Have a clearly stated secure, sustainability plan, providing long term service - for example Zenodo’s services are currently indicated to be available for at least the next 20 years and is linked to the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN.⁴³

Figure 3: Accessible

Making data Interoperable

Making data **Interoperable** relates to ensuring the appropriate use of common formats and standards and describing or categorising data with agreed terms which are documented within open controlled vocabularies. E-RIHS will take the following steps to improve the Interoperability of the data produced in relation to E-RIHS.

³⁹ The <https://re3data.org> tool can be used to find alternative repositories that are compliant with the EU obligations.

⁴⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/e-rihs>

⁴¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Handle_System

⁴² <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

⁴³ <https://home.cern/>

- Standard and open file formats will be used whenever practicable - for less common formats references and links to relevant documentation will be provided.
- The standards used within a given data set shall be documented or referenced as part of the discoverable metadata attached to E-RIHS data.
- Non-standard or proprietary formats will also be listed along with links to appropriate descriptions of the formats used.
- Where possible all categories, keywords and/or terms used to describe or define E-RIHS data shall be selected from or connected to existing publicly linkable vocabularies such as the E-RIHS Vocabulary Server.
- New or non-standard categories, keywords and/or terms required to describe or define E-RIHS shall be added to existing open vocabularies or published as part of the E-RIHS vocabulary.
- E-RIHS will collaborate with future initiatives and projects to improve its use and understanding of practicable interoperability, this work will be widely disseminated to improve the interoperability of related work and data.

Figure 4:
Interoperable

Making data Reusable

Making data Reusable relates to ensuring that data are well documented and clearly licenced. E-RIHS will take the following steps to improve the Reusability of the data produced in relationship to E-RIHS.

- Within E-RIHS, where possible all data shall be published/released under an open Creative Commons licence⁴⁴, or an agreed equivalent licence, preferably [CC-BY](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) or released under [CC-0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/).
- All data published/released by or in association with E-RIHS shall have a clear right statement⁴⁵ attached to it.
- If the actual data are embargoed for an agreed period, this time shall be documented and indicated as part of any registered metadata.
- Any required citation or acknowledgements statements will be clearly defined and documented as metadata.
- Where it is not possible for the actual data to be released, due to agreed and documented “legitimate interests”, the data documentation, published with its metadata, will clearly

Figure 5: Reusable

⁴⁴ <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/>

⁴⁵ <https://rightsstatements.org/>

describe any limitations for reuse and indicate, when there is a specific time related limitation, when the data will be available for reuse.

Other General Access Restriction

As data are gathered and created within E-RIHS some specific access restrictions and limitations relating to existing IPR or legitimate interests may be identified. Where these restrictions and limitations are shown to relate to multiple datasets or to E-RIHS, they will be added to future versions of this document. As noted, before, it is envisaged that this DMP will be linked to more detailed or specific DMPs created for individual E-RIHS National Nodes⁴⁶, services providers and future related research and access projects.

E-RIHS CORE “DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE” SERVICES

At this time the various digital services outlined in this section are generally hosted by an individual member of E-RIHS and the content of the systems are subject to the local back-up and sustainability plans followed by the hosting institution.

Discussions are underway to provide cross institutional support going forward, with multiple partners hosting copies, duplicates and or backups of key systems. Further details of this setup will be added to future versions of this DMP as appropriate.

Public E-RIHS Web Namespaces

MAIN E-RIHS NAMESPACE: E-RIHS.EU

The e-rihs.eu namespace has been setup to be the home of the main E-RIHS public website (<https://www.e-rihs.eu>). It is up and running and includes its own privacy and cookies policies. The namespace **e-rihs.eu**⁴⁷, currently owned and hosted by Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), will be managed by the E-RIHS Central Hub.

In addition to general communications and information the main E-RIHS website will also provide access to the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services and the digital resources of the HS Academy.

E-RIHS Catalogue of Services

The E-RIHS Catalogue of Service will act as the main portal for users to explore the services and resources being offered by E-RIHS. It is currently in the final stages of development, but it is anticipated that the core metadata underpinning it will be linked to the core related metadata stored and managed in the E-RIHS Metadata Knowledge-Base. Data related to the offered services, along with future calls for applications and the resultant proposals will be metadata will be maintained as described for other management data. Details related to successful projects will be managed as E-RIHS Results (Foreground Data).

⁴⁶ <https://www.e-rihs.eu/national-nodes/>

⁴⁷ <https://whois.domaintools.com/e-rihs.eu>

Deliverable D5.2

HS (Heritage Science) Academy

The initiative HS Academy covers a wide range of cutting–edge training opportunities in Heritage Science and has two main objectives:

- Inform potential users of E-RIHS services and the scientific instruments and tools they make available.
- Provide training on specific subjects of interest to the Heritage Science community.

The wider variety of video based material or relevant webinars, lectures and discussions are hosted on YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/c/ERIHSEU>) and are managed subject to their terms and conditions.

Metadata relating to these resources is also hosted and managed on the E-RIHS and IPERION-HS websites. A more unified presentation is anticipated as E-RIHS develops. This metadata will be maintained as described for other management data.

Sub-domains e-rihs.eu

There are no sub-domains of e-rihs.eu currently register with the CO.

DIGITAL SERVICES E-RIHS NAMESPACE: E-RIHS.IO

The e-rihs.io namespace has been setup to be the home of core E-RIHS digital services and related documentation. The namespace **e-rihs.io**⁴⁸ is registered and managed by the KIK-IRPA for E-RIHS and will also be maintained as described for other management data. At this time, it is also planned to be the home for various lists of related E-RIHS digital resources, software, and services as well as external digital resources that are used by or may be of use to the E-RIHS community.

The main url, <https://e-rihs.io>, currently acts as a test landing page for information about the developing E-RIHS digital infrastructure, but this will be revisited as E-RIHS develops. This website and all the related code is hosted on GitHub (<https://github.com/E-RIHS/e-rihs.github.io>), the code has also been backed up by the developers working on it. It is anticipated that as the content of the cite develops beyond the initial testing phase the code will also be periodically backed up on Zenodo.

Sub-domains e-rihs.io

The following sub-domains of e-rihs.io have been setup in relation specific defined services.

Namespace	Service	Main Host
hdl.e-rihs.io	Handle based Persistent Identifier service, see below	KIK-IRPA
vocab.e-rihs.io	Vocabulary and controlled list service, see below	C2RMF
data.e-rihs.io	Core metadata management service, see below	KIK-IRPA

REGISTERED COUNTRY CODE VERSIONS

In relation to a range of possible National E-RIHS related activities a number of country code specific E-RIHS URLs have been registered. The services and information provided via these URLs are not centrally managed by the E-RIHS Central Hub and are listed here for information. However, it is

⁴⁸ <https://whois.domaintools.com/e-rihs.io>

recommended that more detailed collaboration and discussion related to how these namespaces are used, in relation to E-RIHS, should be developed and described here as E-RIHS develops.

Namespace	National Node	Live URL or Comment
e-rihs.it	Italy	https://www.e-rihs.it
e-rihs.fr	France	https://www.erihs.fr
e-rihs.gr	Greece	https://www.e-rihs.gr
e-rihs.hu	Hungary	https://e-rihs.hu
e-rihs.mt	Malta	https://erihs.gov.mt
e-rihs.nl	Netherlands	https://e-rihs.nl
e-rihs.pl	Poland	http://www.e-rihs.pl
e-rihs.pt	Portugal	Registered but does not resolve to a live website
e-rihs.ro	Romania	https://e-rihs.ro/
e-rihs.es	Spain	http://www.e-rihs.es
e-rihs.si	Slovenia	https://www.e-rihs.si
e-rihs.uk	United Kingdom	Not currently registered
e-rihs.cy	Cyprus	https://erihs.cyi.ac.cy
e-rihs.be	Belgium	https://e-rihs.be (resolves to https://www.e-rihs.eu/national-nodes/belgium/ in anticipation of a dedicated local website)

E-RIHS Persistent Identifiers

A system to provide and manage PIDs for E-RIHS has been setup based on the handle system. The handle system is a decentralised system for managing persistent identifiers (PIDs). Originally developed by the [Corporation for National Research Initiatives](#) (CNRI, Reston VI, USA), the Global handle Registry (GHR) is now governed and maintained by the [DONA Foundation](#) (Geneva, Switzerland), together with multiple organisations that are credentialed and authorized by DONA. Each of those organisations are referred to as Multi-Primary Administrators (MPAs). Key MPAs are CNRI, the [International DOI Foundation](#) and the Gesellschaft Für Wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung [MBH Göttingen](#) (GWDG). The latter represents the European [PIDconsortium](#), managing the ePIC system (which are in essence Handles). E-RIHS has been attributed its own prefix ([21.11158](#)) by GWDG/PIDconsortium.

Live system: <https://hdl.e-rihs.io> - Please note, that though live this root directory does not resolve to a user friendly web page at this time.

Software: **Handle.Net software distribution**

- Documentation: https://www.handle.net/hnr_documentation.html
- Source code: <https://www.handle.net/hnr-source/handle-9.3.1-distribution.tar.gz>
- Licence: [Handle.net Public License v2](#) (open source)

Hosted by: KIK-IRPA

Managed by: KIK-IRPA

E-RIHS Vocabulary Server

To provide a persistent single source for the terms and keywords used to describe future E-RIHS activities and within E-RIHS tools and services a dedicated vocabulary server has been setup for E-RIHS. At this time, it is being primarily used as a source for controlled lists, but the system is SKOS compliant and could be expanded into a full E-RIHS hierarchical vocabulary in the future if required. The system has also been connected to the E-RIHS persistent identifier system to ensure that all the terms and groups recorded in the system can be referenced using E-RIHS PIDs.

Where possible the terms used within this system are referenced from existing open vocabularies. Where these exact matches occur the source PID for each term is included within the E-RIHS term record.

External sources currently include, but are not limited to:

- The Getty Linked Open Data vocabularies: <https://vocab.getty.edu/>
- Wikidata: <https://www.wikidata.org/>

Live system: <https://vocab.e-rihs.io>

Software: **Opentheso2**

- Documentation: <https://opentheso.hypotheses.org/>
- Source code: <https://github.com/miledrousset/Opentheso2>
- Licence: http://www.cecill.info/licences/Licence_CeCILL-C_V1-en.html (open source compatible with the GNU GPL license)

Hosted by: C2RMF

Managed by: NG, KIK-IRPA, FORTH

CONTROLLED LIST DATA PRESENTATION

The use of the data stored within vocabulary system is also supported by an additional E-RIHS tool to reformat the data provided by the OpenTheso2 API. This system was put in place to simplify the format of the published data but also to improve sustainability but ensuring that the published terms could continue to be used even if the underlying vocabulary server needed to be replaced in the future.

Live system: <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11158/0003-a375-bce0-4571>

Software: **E-RIHS Controlled Lists**

- Documentation: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/controlled-lists/blob/main/README.md>
- Source code: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/controlled-lists>
- Licence: MIT: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/controlled-lists?tab=MIT-1-ov-file>

Hosted by: NG

Managed by: NG

E-RIHS Metadata Knowledge-Base

The E-RIHS Knowledge-base is a developing advanced repository designed to facilitate the sharing and discovery of information pertaining to the E-RIHS infrastructure, services, and resources. This

Knowledge-base will be integral to the E-RIHS community, supporting the efficient dissemination and retrieval of critical data and metadata. Powered by Cordra⁴⁹, a sophisticated platform for managing digital objects, the Knowledge-base leverages Cordra's capabilities to create, manage, and share digital objects effectively. Cordra provides a versatile and extensible framework, making it ideal for constructing robust digital repositories that can accommodate the diverse needs of heritage science research.

The primary objective of the E-RIHS Knowledge-base is to streamline the process of capturing, storing, and reusing metadata. This facilitates the definition and output of E-RIHS heritage science research as FAIR Digital Objects (DO). By enabling automatic tagging of research results and data with predefined metadata—describing the context, personnel, equipment, methods, and other relevant factors—the Knowledge-base will significantly simplify the documentation process for individual analyses. In essence, this system reduces the manual overhead associated with metadata documentation. As the metadata for various elements such as equipment and methods are predefined within the Knowledge-base, they can be easily reused and associated with new research outputs. This not only enhances efficiency but also ensures consistency and accuracy in the documentation of heritage science research, thereby fostering a more collaborative and transparent research environment.

The E-RIHS Knowledge-base stands as a pivotal resource in the heritage science domain, promoting better management and utilization of research data and metadata, and ultimately contributing to the advancement of the field through improved data accessibility and interoperability.

The E-RIHS Knowledge-base has been configured to use ORCID iD for authentication.

Live system: <https://data.e-rihs.io>

Software: **Cordra**

- Documentation: <https://www.cordra.org/documentation/introduction/introduction.html>
- Source code: <https://gitlab.com/cnri/cordra/cordra>
- Licence: Apache Licence 2.0 (<https://gitlab.com/cnri/cordra/cordra/-/blob/master/LICENSE.txt>)

Hosted by: KIK-IRPA

Managed by: KIK-IRPA, with contributions from NG and FORTH

E-RIHS METADATA SCHEMA

The structure of the data stored within the E-RIHS Knowledge-base is defined by a series of E-RIHS JSON Schema, which were initially developed during the IPERION-HS and E-RIHS IP EU projects. This work has concentrated on defining the core metadata required to defined key aspects of Heritage Science research, specifically in relation to the activities of E-RIHS. Individual schema documents have been created to define each key aspect, such a Services, People, Methods, Equipment, etc. These schema documents are used by the E-RIHS Metadata Knowledge-Base to automatically create, and link together, metadata entry forms that can be used to document Heritage Science activities.

⁴⁹ <https://www.cordra.org/>

Deliverable D5.2

These data schemas are publicly available on GitHub and can be used to by others in the community to generate additional interoperable software solutions. The E-RIHS Catalogue of Service system, currently in development, will link to the E-RIHS Metadata Knowledge-Base via these schemas.

- The current versions of the schema used are presented at: <https://e-rihs.io/schema>
- The GitHub repository can be found at: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/schema>

Graphical representations⁵⁰ of the development of these metadata schemas can also be found on GitHub at:

- <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/blob/main/Shared%20Models/README.md>

E-RIHS Community Forum

Various communication platforms have been used during the development of E-RIHS (for example within the IPERION-HS and E-RIHS IP), but these have generally been closed systems, used to manage communications between project partners. It has been anticipated that a more open discussion forum may well be required for the broader more open community within the E-RIHS ERIC. Several options have been tested in relation to the different levels of discussion that may well be useful, such as:

- A linked in company has been setup (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/e-rihs/>) to act as the E-RIHS hub for discussion on LinkedIn.
- Similarly, the E-RIHS X (Twitter) account [@ErihsEu](https://twitter.com/ErihsEu) to act as the E-RIHS hub for discussion on X (Twitter).

Additionally, a more experimental digital forum has been tested during the IPERION-HS project using the <https://zulip.com/> platform. Zulip is an open-source team chat application designed for real-time and asynchronous communication, featuring topic-based threading within channels. Zulip sponsors cloud-based versions of their platform for research projects and one of these have been setup for testing purposes.

- <https://e-rihs.zulipchat.com/> (A registered account is required for use at this time)

It is also possible for this system to be self-hosted, and it is anticipated that if this system is exploited to a greater extent within E-RIHS, as it develops, a self-hosted version may be setup within the E-RIHS Hub or with an appropriate E-RIHS partners and managed to ensure the stored data can be FAIR and GDPR compliant.

ACCESS RELATED DATA MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS IN E-RIHS

Specific embargoes, caveats and additional complications identified across E-RIHS LABs or as part of other specific future E-RIHS activities will be detailed within dedicated DMPs and or added to this section if they represent generic issues relating to multiple E-RIHS activities.

⁵⁰ This work is also backed up on Zenodo at: Padfield, J., Sotiropoulou, S., Fremout, W., & Schmidle, W. (2024). E-RIHS Heritage Science Interoperability (v0.5-beta). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7221155>

E-RIHS Access LABs

E-RIHS offers Access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, methodologies, data and tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in the field of Heritage Science⁵¹. Within E-RIHS each Access has the potential to generate a wide variety of data from raw data to finished publications. The management of all the actual E-RIHS data will generally follow the steps outlined in this document, but it is expected that some types of Access or even specific Accesses made need to outline exceptions or even additional DM steps. These additional DMPs or references to them will be collected and published by the E-RIHS Central Hub. They will also be connected to or referenced within relevant E-RIHS datasets.

As indicated before, User Reports⁵² created at the end of each Access will be published by E-RIHS within the chosen E-RIHS data repository.

ARCHLAB⁵³

In general DM issues related to ARCHLAB accesses closely follow the details set out in this general document, however this will continue to be explored with E-RIHS. Work in this area could include but may not be limited to issues of exploiting Background data, integrating archive DMPs and IPR issues, and recommendations of how new data created by E-RIHS Users after a given Access can be linked back to E-RIHS. Further general ARCHLAB related details will be added to this section during the development of E-RIHS. As noted, details of specific DM issues related to individual services or access projects should be documented separately and the details passed on to the E-RIHS Central Hub to ensure sure they can be connected to or referenced within relevant E-RIHS datasets.

FIXLAB⁵⁴

In general DM issues related to FIXLAB accesses closely follow the details set out in this general document, however this will continue to be explored with E-RIHS. Work in this area could include but may not be limited to issues of dealing with larger amounts of data, sample descriptions and integrating with existing DMPs used by larger scale research facilities. As noted, details of specific DM issues related to individual services or access projects should be documented separately and the details passed on to the E-RIHS Central Hub to ensure sure they can be connected to or referenced within relevant E-RIHS datasets.

MOLAB⁵⁵

In general DM issues related to MOLAB accesses closely follow the details set out in this general document, however this will continue to be explored with E-RIHS. Work in this area could include

⁵¹ <https://www.e-rihs.eu/catalogue-of-services/>

⁵² An updated description will be provided on the E-RIHS website based on the information already provided by projects developed by the E-RIHS community, see <http://www.iperionhs.eu/after-access/> and https://www.iperionhs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/IPERION-HS_User-Report_TEMPLATE.pdf

⁵³ <http://www.iperionhs.eu/archlab/> - An updated version of this description will be provided on the E-RIHS public website.

⁵⁴ <http://www.iperionhs.eu/fixlab/> - An updated version of this description will be provided on the E-RIHS public website.

⁵⁵ <http://www.iperionhs.eu/molab/> - An updated version of this description will be provided on the E-RIHS public website.

but may not be limited to issues of managing data in a mobile environment, integrating data from different techniques and issues of storing and presenting the captured data. As noted, details of specific DM issues related to individual services or access projects should be documented separately and the details passed on to the E-RIHS Central Hub to ensure sure they can be connected to or referenced within relevant E-RIHS datasets.

DIGILAB

DIGLAB is a new service platform which will begin within E-RIHS. It is intended that DIGLAB will offer a range of digital services and expertise and represent the organisation of the digital infrastructure for E-RIHS. Work in this area is expected to mirror many of the issues related to the other LABs but could also include though not limited to issues of dealing with multiple versions of similar datasets, online tools, developing software and the collaboration with existing digital services within other infrastructures. In general, it is anticipated that DM issues related to DIGILAB accesses will closely follow the details set out in this general document, however this will continue to be explored with E-RIHS.

FUTURE ACTIVITIES: RESEARCH PROJECTS AND COLLABORATIONS

Moving beyond the general DM issues relating to accesses provided by E-RHIS, it is also crucial to account for several key additional considerations to ensure the successful integration and management of data in relation to future projects and collaborations.

Firstly, scalability of data management practices must be prioritized to handle increasing volumes and varieties of data. This involves investing in robust and flexible infrastructure that can adapt to evolving data requirements.

Secondly, clear, and comprehensive data governance policies should be established and consistently updated to reflect best practices and regulatory changes. These policies will ensure data integrity, security, and compliance across all projects.

Additionally, fostering a culture of collaboration and communication between all stakeholders is essential. This includes setting up standardized protocols for data sharing and collaboration, ensuring transparency, and facilitating seamless data integration from multiple sources. Intellectual property rights and data ownership must also be clearly defined to avoid conflicts and ensure fair usage.

Future projects may involve partnerships with external entities, making it important to assess and align with their data management policies and practices. Data interoperability and compatibility should be considered to enable smooth collaboration. Finally, ongoing training and capacity building for team members will be necessary to keep up with technological advancements and emerging trends in data management.

By addressing these areas, we can create a sustainable and forward-looking data management framework that supports innovation and enhances the value derived from our data assets.

REFERENCES

- European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science: <http://www.e-rihs.eu>
- Heritage Data Reuse Charter: <https://www.dariah.eu/tools-services/data-re-use/>
- The FAIR Principles - Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable - <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
- Benassi, Laura. (2021, January 16). IPERION HS How to do - Open Science: EU rules and tips (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4444799> - <http://www.iperionhs.eu/publications-2/open-access/>
- The EU's open science policy - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en
- What is the Cultural Heritage Cloud? - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en
- Annotated model GA (version 1.0, 1 May 2024) https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf
- H2020 How to define and Manage Background - <http://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/news/how-define-and-manage-background-horizon-2020>
- Padfield, J. (2021). D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788560>
- H2020 Open access & Data management: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm
- EU support for open access - <http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=openaccess>
- Final report and recommendations of the Commission 2nd High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), 2018 - <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1>